

1 **Control of global temperature in concentration-driven climate models**

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25 **Abstract.**

26 We present two methods to generate time-varying carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentrations in order to drive an
27 atmosphere-ocean general circulation model (AOGCM) to a desired target timeseries of global mean surface
28 temperature. Specifically, we consider targets of a linear rampup rate of surface temperature, stabilisation at a given
29 target temperature, and ramp down at a fixed rate after a period of stabilisation, as proposed for standard
30 experiments of the Tipping Point Model Intercomparison Project (TIPMIP). The first method method pre-calculates
31 the required concentration timeseries using an energy balance model fitted to a commonly-performed AOGCM
32 experiment (instantaneous CO₂ quadrupling). We present the calibrated energy balance model parameters for all
33 available CMIP6 models. The second method uses adaptive control to maintain the desired temperature. We
34 compare the properties of our two methods with each other, and with a recently proposed emissions-driven method
35 aiming at the same target temperature timeseries.

36

37 **1 Introduction**

38

39 As global climate continues to warm through the first part of the 21st Century (IPCC, 2021), the challenges of
40 limiting anthropogenic climate change become ever more pressing. To inform evidence-based action, increasing
41 detail is needed on the consequences and risks of different climate pathways. In recent years there has been
42 increasing interest in emissions pathways that may lead to stabilisation of global mean surface temperature above
43 an assumed pre-industrial baseline at different target levels. This includes ‘overshoot’ pathways under which the
44 temperature exceeds the target level for some period before falling back to the target (IPCC, 2021). In this paper
45 we refer to the time-dependent surface air temperature (SAT) anomaly above its pre-industrial value, and use
46 ‘Global Warming Level’ or GWL to describe an actuarial or targeted long-term stable SAT anomaly.

47

48 Interest in overshoots is motivated by the policy ambition to attain specific target GWLs such as the 1.5°C and
49 2.0°C targets of the 2015 Paris agreement <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement> ,
50 combined with the realisation that *peak* warming levels are determined by a remaining carbon budget that is
51 currently being rapidly used up (Allen et al. 2009 , IPCC, 2021). Different emissions pathways leading to the
52 same eventual GWL may result in different outcomes, especially in terms of committed long-term changes to
53 slow components of the climate system such as ice sheets, sea level and ocean circulation (Fox-Kemper et al
54 2021). A particular cause for concern is the possibility that temporarily exceeding specific GWLs may result in
55 the crossing of a so-called ‘tipping point’ (Armstrong McKay et al 2022, Loriani et al 2025) which results in a
56 commitment to major system changes, potentially even after GWLs are stabilised or reduced (e.g. Robinson et al.
57 2012, Bochow et al. 2023, Höning et al. 2023, Klose et al. 2024, Ritchie et al. 2021, Romanou et al. 2023,
58 Drijfhout et al. 2025).

59

60 To address the currently fragmented knowledge and deep uncertainty surrounding tipping points (IPCC, 2021),
61 Winkelmann et al (2026) have recently proposed a coordinated Tipping Points Model Intercomparison Project
62 TIPMIP. TIPMIP follows the long-established approach of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project CMIP
63 (Dunne et al. 2025), in defining a set of standard climate model experiments to be performed by multiple
64 modelling groups, so allowing an assessment of the range of model responses in a particular scenario, and
65 analysis of the key model processes that are responsible for that range.

66

67 Within TIPMIP, a particular experimental protocol has been defined for comprehensive Earth System Models
68 (ESMs) referred to here as TIPMIP-ESM (Jones et al. 2026, hereafter J26). A novel feature of TIPMIP-ESM is
69 that it is defined by target timeseries of GWL, rather than the more traditional timeseries of emissions or
70 concentrations of greenhouse gases, aerosols and other radiative forcing agents. Advantages of this approach are
71 that GWL is easier to relate to policy targets such as those of the Paris agreement, and that the tipping dynamics
72 in the different models are separated out from uncertainties in the global climate response to emissions or
73 concentrations, such as climate sensitivity or transient response to carbon emissions (Sanderson et al. 2024). A
74 potential practical disadvantage is that because climate models are typically driven by emissions or
75 concentrations of forcing agents, it is not obvious *a priori* how to specify the forcing of a given model to achieve
76 the target GWL timeseries.

77
78 The TIPMIP-ESM protocol specifies a specific, idealised timeseries of GWL, consisting of a ‘ramp-up’ phase in
79 which the global mean surface air temperature (SAT) increases at a specified rate, a ‘stabilisation’ phase in which
80 SAT remains constant at a specified value (i.e. the target GWL), and a ‘ramp-down’ phase in which SAT reduces.
81 This may be followed by a further period of stabilisation at a lower GWL, an idealised representation of SAT
82 stabilisation following an overshoot. The scenario is illustrated in Figure 1 of J26. A further idealisation is that
83 SAT is assumed in this protocol to be forced entirely by increased CO₂, relative to the pre-industrial control
84 climate, neglecting other climate forcing factors.

85
86 J26 describe how a target GWL can be achieved approximately in a model that includes an interactive carbon
87 cycle, so that the forcing can be prescribed in terms of CO₂ *emissions* rather than *concentrations*. This takes
88 advantage of the observations that first, in the ramp-up phase, SAT anomaly is approximately proportional to
89 cumulative emissions, with a model-dependent constant of proportionality known as Transient Climate Response
90 to CO₂ Emissions (TCRE, Allen et al 2009); and secondly, approximate stabilisation of GWL is frequently seen
91 when CO₂ emissions are set to zero (i.e. the Zero Emissions Commitment or ZEC is often approximately zero,
92 especially at lower GWLs, MacDougall et al. 2020). This allows a simple specification of CO₂ emissions that can
93 be expected to result approximately in the desired SAT ramp-up and stabilisation, i.e. constant emissions at a
94 given rate (depending on the model’s TCRE) in the ramp-up stage, followed by zero emissions in the stabilisation
95 stage. The ramp-down stage is specified as negative emissions at the opposite rate to the ramp-up. This simplicity
96 of specification is important to encourage the widest possible participation in the experiment, and it is accepted
97 that the SAT will not follow the specified timeseries exactly. This approach offers practical simplicity compared

98 to adaptive emissions control methods (AERA-MIP, Silvy et al. 2024), which achieve closer tracking of a target
99 SAT timeseries through continuous control calculation within the model runs.

100

101 Many climate models do not include an interactive carbon cycle, particularly high resolution models, for which
102 the computational expense of biogeochemical calculations and spinup would be prohibitive (e.g. HighResMIP,
103 Roberts et al 2025). Such models explore important aspects of the physics of climate tipping points, but require a
104 forcing in terms of CO₂ *concentrations* rather than emissions. The purpose of this paper is to specify two methods
105 to calculate a CO₂ concentration timeseries for a given model, to produce the SATs specified in the TIPMIP-ESM
106 protocol. We anticipate that these methods will be applicable more widely beyond the TIPMIP project. The first
107 method (denoted P, Section 2) pre-calculates CO₂ concentration as a function of time, with parameters that can be
108 derived for each model from standard CMIP runs (Eyring et al. 2016). We present values for these parameters
109 from a wide range of CMIP6 climate models, and show how they can be simply calculated for other models. The
110 second method (denoted A, Section 3) adopts an adaptive control method similar to that of Silvy et al (2024), but
111 based on concentrations. Section 4 presents a comparison of these approaches with each other and with related
112 protocols such as the emissions-driven protocols of J26 and Silvy et al (2024). Given the emphasis on easy
113 implementation and acceptance of approximate conformance to the target SAT timeseries, we propose that either
114 method (P or A) is acceptable for TIPMIP-ESM experiments and for other concentration-driven experiments
115 aiming to reproduce specific GWLs. Section 5 discusses practical issues including experiment and file naming
116 conventions, and Section 6 summarises our conclusions.

117

118 Throughout this paper we refer to complex climate models of the type studied by CMIP as Atmosphere-Ocean
119 General Circulation Models (AOGCMs). We allow this term to include models both with and without an
120 interactive carbon cycle, as the former can often be run in concentration-driven (“c-driven”) as well as emissions-
121 driven (“e-driven”) mode.

122

123

124 **2 Method P (Prescribed): Pre-calculated forcing timeseries from an Energy Balance Model**

125 In this method, the CO₂ concentration timeseries is calculated in advance using a simple formula, calculated by
126 inserting the desired GMST profile (linear rampup or constant) into the simple 2-layer energy balance model
127 (EBM) of Geoffroy et al. (2013), hereafter G13. This model considers the climate system as upper and deep
128 global ocean boxes, with the upper ocean box temperatures controlled by a simple radiative exchange with the

129 atmosphere/space, and by mixing with the deep box. Temperatures of both boxes are considered to be anomalies
 130 from some assumed equilibrium (pre-industrial) state. This EBM does a good job in predicting the SAT
 131 responses to instantaneous CO₂ quadrupling and 1% per annum CO₂ concentration increase, in the sixteen
 132 AOGCMs studied (see Figure 2 of G13), suggesting that it is a suitable tool for predicting the global responses
 133 that we are interested in. We adopt the same notation as in G13 equations (1) and (2), which define the EBM. For
 134 convenience these equations are repeated here:

135

$$136 \quad C \frac{dT}{dt} = F - \lambda T - \gamma(T - T_0) \quad (1)$$

137

$$138 \quad C_0 \frac{dT_0}{dt} = \gamma(T - T_0) \quad (2)$$

139

140 where

141 $T(t)$ = temperature anomaly (vs the pre-industrial control) of upper EBM ocean box (assumed here to be
 142 equivalent to the GMST anomaly)

143 $T_0(t)$ = temperature anomaly of lower EBM ocean box

144 $F(t)$ = Effective Radiative Forcing (Wm⁻²) (simply converted to CO₂ concentration, see Section 2.4 below)

145 C = Heat capacity of upper box (Jm⁻²K⁻¹)

146 C_0 = Heat capacity of lower box (Jm⁻²K⁻¹)

147 λ = Climate feedback parameter or CFP (Wm⁻²K⁻¹) – sign convention taken as positive for positive climate
 148 sensitivity

149 γ = Ocean vertical transfer coefficient (Wm⁻²K⁻¹)

150

151 For any given AOGCM, the corresponding EBM parameters are estimated by fitting to the time-dependent SAT
 152 response in the AOGCM instantaneous 4xCO₂ experiment. See Section 3a of G13 for details.

153

154 **2.1 Temperature rampup stage:**

155 Substituting a solution of the form $T = kt$, for a linearly increasing temperature at rate k in Ks⁻¹ with t being time
 156 in s, into (1) and (2), and solving for the effective radiative forcing F , gives

$$157 \quad F(t) = k(C_0 + C) + \lambda kt - kC_0 e^{-\frac{\gamma t}{C_0}} \quad (3)$$

158

159 Note that there is an instantaneous increase in F by kC at $t=0$, to counteract the initial thermal inertia of the
 160 system and give a smooth linear temperature increase.

161

162 It is recognised that for practical reasons modelling groups may choose to start the temperature stabilisation phase
 163 after a different rampup. One reason to do this would be to make use of existing CMIP *1pctCO2* runs (Eyring et
 164 al. 2016) for the rampup phase. This gives a faster temperature rampup than 0.2 degC/decade in most CMIP
 165 models.

166

167 For the case of a linear rampup, a simple linear approximation

168

$$169 \quad \frac{d(CO_2)}{dt} = k \frac{CO_2^{pic}}{TCR} \quad (4)$$

170

171 has been found to give a reasonable results, where $CO_2(t)$ is the CO_2 concentration, CO_2^{pic}
 172 is its pre-industrial value, and TCR is the Transient Climate Response of the model (Meehl et al. 2020). Equation
 173 (4) requires only knowledge of the TCR (from the model's *1pctCO2* run) and the pre-industrial CO_2
 174 concentration. For models with $TCR > 1.4$ deg C (lower than nearly all CMIP6 models, Meehl et al. 2020),
 175 equation (4) implies a rate of CO_2 increase that is less than 1% of the pre-industrial value per annum. The
 176 different temperature responses for rampup of CO_2 concentration at 1% per annum, 0.5% per annum, and eqn (4),
 177 are illustrated in Fig. F.5 for the intermediate complexity model CLIMBER-2 (Ganopolski and Brovkin, 2017),
 178 which has a TCR of 1.8 deg C.

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180

181 **2.2 Temperature stabilisation stage:**

182 We now seek a solution to (1) and (2) of form $T = \underline{T}$ (*constant*) from time t_0 onwards. We obtain

$$183 \quad F(t) = \lambda \underline{T} + A e^{-\frac{\gamma t^*}{c_0}} \quad (5)$$

184

185 where $t^* = t - t_0$, and the constant A is chosen so that $F(t_0)$ is continuous with the previous stage of the run (i.e. the
 186 forcing or CO_2 concentration at the end of the rampup stage).

187

188 We could alternatively impose continuity of T_0 , rather than of F , but this results in considerable algebraic
 189 complication for a general rampup phase. Continuity of F results in a slight overshoot of the target temperature T
 190 (see Fig. F1), which is greatest following a faster rampup. Continuity of forcing is more consistent with the e-
 191 driven scenario (J26), and the temperature overshoot is of a similar or smaller magnitude to those seen in that
 192 case (e.g. see Figure 4 of J26). Note also that with continuity of F the solution for the stabilisation phase is
 193 independent of the details of the rampup, so (5) can be used for stabilisation runs branched off *any* rampup run
 194 (e.g. standard 1% CO₂ increase runs). Hence continuity of F is considered to be a pragmatic approach that gives
 195 an acceptable approximation for the purposes of TIPMIP.

196
 197 We define the end time t_0 of the rampup stage in the same way as for the e-driven scenario (J26), i.e. the first year
 198 in which the 31-year centred mean, global mean surface air temperature anomaly (GMSAT) exceeds the 31-year
 199 centred mean GMSAT in the pre-industrial control run at the year from which the rampup run is started. In
 200 practice, we would then impose continuity of CO₂ concentration at t_0 , convert this to $F(t_0)$ using (9) below,
 201 substitute in (5) at $t = t_0$ to determine A , then convert $F(t)$ from (5) back to $CO_2(t)$ using (9).

202

203 2.3 Temperature rampdown stage

204 While the focus of this study is on the temperature stabilisation phase, we also propose here a protocol for a
 205 ‘rampdown’ phase following a period of temperature stabilisation. We assume that T is held constant $T = \underline{T}$ for
 206 some years until $t=t_1$, then ramped down at a rate k Ks⁻¹, i.e.

207 $T = \underline{T} - k(t - t_1)$. We obtain

208

$$209 F(t^{**}) = [\lambda \underline{T} - k(C + C_0)] - \lambda k t^{**} + B e^{-\frac{\gamma}{c_0} t^{**}} \quad (7)$$

210

211 where $t^{**} = t - t_1$. We again choose the constant B to impose continuity of F (or CO₂ concentration) at the start of
 212 the rampdown phase $t^{**}=0$, i.e.

213

$$214 B = F(t_1) - \lambda \underline{T} + k(C + C_0) \quad (8)$$

215

216 Other choices for the rampdown are possible, e.g. reducing CO₂ concentrations at the same rate as the rampup.
 217 There is less direct analogy here with the e-driven scenario (J26), which ramps down emissions at the same rate

218 as the rampup, because the emissions rampdown is not expected to produce a linear temperature rampdown, nor
 219 is the response expected to be similar between different models. We therefore accept that the temperature during
 220 the rampdown phase in e-driven models may be less constrained by the emissions scenario, and propose here an
 221 approach in which the temperature rampdown *is* similar between models, by construction. This will allow a
 222 comparison of model responses that does not convolute tipping dynamics with global radiative and carbon cycle
 223 feedbacks, and so potentially give complementary insights to the e-driven rampdown.

224

225 **2.4 Conversion of F(t) to CO₂ concentration:**

226 Within the simple nature of our model, we assume that effective radiative forcing F increases logarithmically
 227 with CO₂ concentration:

228

$$229 \quad F(t) = \frac{F_{4x}}{\ln 4} \ln \left(\frac{CO_2(t)}{CO_2^{pic}} \right) \quad (9)$$

230

231 where F_{4x} is the radiative forcing at four times pre-industrial CO₂. Rearranging gives:

232

$$233 \quad CO_2(t) = CO_2^{pic} e^{\frac{\ln 4 F(t)}{F_{4x}}}. \quad (10)$$

234

235 Other multipliers than 4 can be used for the high-CO₂ state, with n times CO₂, and effective radiative forcing F_{nx}
 236 ($n > 4$ is possible in principle, but in a realistic radiation model, the forcing will become more sensitive to CO₂
 237 than Eq. 9-10 capture (Zhong and Haigh, 2013)). The factor 4 is used here because the commonly-run CMIP
 238 scenario *abrupt-4xCO2* allows the model parameters λ (climate feedback parameter) and F_{4x} (the ERF) to be
 239 derived by a standard method (see below).

240

241 **2.5 EBM parameter values for CMIP6 models:**

242 The full solution for $CO_2(t)$ from (3, 5, 7- 9) requires knowledge of the EBM parameters C , C_0 , λ , γ and F_{4x} .

243 These were calculated in G13 for the sixteen AOGCMs studied in that paper, by calibrating to the response of
 244 each model in the standard CMIP instantaneous CO₂ quadrupling experiment (*abrupt-4xCO2*, see e.g. Eyring et
 245 al 2016). Here, we have performed a similar calibration for 58 available CMIP6 models (Table 1). This will
 246 enable users of any of these models to calculate the required CO₂(t) profiles for that model.

247

248 Overall the multi-model means and standard deviations for these parameters are comparable with those for the
249 older AOGCMs in G13. The mean and maximum *EffCS* are somewhat higher, reflecting the overall higher
250 sensitivity of CMIP6 models (Meehl et al.2020) and there is a somewhat larger range of values for C and C_0 .

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Model	F4x (Wm ⁻²)	λ (Wm ⁻² K ⁻¹)	EffCS (°C)	γ (W m ⁻² K ⁻¹)	C (W yr m ⁻² K ⁻¹)	C ₀ (W yr m ⁻² K ⁻¹)	τ_f (yr)	τ_s (yr)
ACCESS-CM2	6.7255	0.7126	4.7191	0.5856	7.7403	85.2380	5.8516	270.1721
ACCESS-ESM1-5	5.6750	0.7331	3.8704	0.7191	7.2433	82.3216	4.8803	231.7727
AWI-CM1-1-MR	7.7039	1.2384	3.1105	0.5544	7.4211	51.1796	4.0809	135.5474
BCC-CSM2-MR	6.1435	1.0050	3.0564	0.7184	7.5014	69.0164	4.2699	167.9384
BCC-ESM1	6.0594	0.9231	3.2823	0.6369	7.6482	83.4009	4.8274	224.7631
CAMS-CSM1-0	8.1714	1.7901	2.2824	0.6115	9.1070	57.2240	3.7521	126.8761
CAS-ESM2-0	6.3994	0.9120	3.5084	0.5108	6.7421	63.9151	4.6736	197.9348
CESM2-FV2	5.6604	0.5395	5.2456	0.8505	5.4959	80.5511	3.8540	250.3557
CESM2-WACCM-FV2	5.8554	0.6030	4.8555	0.7957	6.1649	98.9996	4.3192	294.5017
CESM2-WACCM	6.5528	0.6901	4.7475	0.8515	6.7255	77.0262	4.2471	207.5726
CESM2	6.7661	0.6556	5.1603	0.7828	6.1887	64.3300	4.1807	185.5653
CIESM	7.7026	0.6809	5.6560	0.7520	7.3313	69.0177	4.9671	198.9372
CMCC-CM2-SR5	7.7927	1.1069	3.5202	0.5557	7.4060	60.0607	4.3922	164.6343
CMCC-ESM2	7.5131	1.0506	3.5756	0.6776	7.1428	56.3134	4.0516	139.4527
CNRM-CM6-1-HR	8.1177	0.9475	4.2837	0.5269	8.7314	103.4915	5.8577	309.0058
CNRM-CM6-1	7.4507	0.7714	4.8294	0.5562	7.0092	120.6008	5.2255	377.0259
CNRM-ESM2-1	5.9793	0.6275	4.7641	0.5897	7.8528	100.2510	6.3329	335.9510
CanESM5	7.3989	0.6588	5.6159	0.5518	7.6364	76.9461	6.1776	261.6652
CanESM5-1	7.1655	0.6380	5.6157	0.5544	7.6132	72.5616	6.2393	250.2979
E3SM-1-0	6.7447	0.6356	5.3055	0.4115	7.6306	39.7810	7.0679	164.1879
E3SM-2-0	6.0608	0.7621	3.9763	0.4023	7.8382	37.9992	6.5620	148.0297
EC-Earth3-AerCh	7.2849	0.9439	3.8592	0.4886	8.1619	45.6855	5.5768	144.9648
EC-Earth3-Veg	6.8201	0.7921	4.3054	0.5378	7.0034	36.9786	5.1010	119.1896
EC-Earth3	6.3871	0.7595	4.2048	0.5668	7.2513	37.1428	5.2703	118.7123
FGOALS-f3-L	8.2353	1.3742	2.9963	0.6361	7.9098	73.3450	3.8915	170.5340
FGOALS-g3	7.2100	1.2543	2.8740	0.7238	7.4599	102.1010	3.7341	224.6842
FIO-ESM-2-0	7.4730	0.8872	4.2115	0.7888	7.1433	85.3382	4.1829	208.2427
GFDL-CM4	6.5293	0.8429	3.8733	0.6943	5.5585	80.5037	3.5650	214.4886
GFDL-ESM4	6.9651	1.2800	2.7207	0.6371	7.9979	117.8074	4.1404	279.0653
GISS-E2-1-G	7.8443	1.4426	2.7188	0.8735	6.2341	139.7764	2.6745	258.5588
GISS-E2-1-H	7.0773	1.1370	3.1123	0.6756	8.1573	78.9685	4.4351	189.0780
GISS-E2-2-G	7.4370	1.5412	2.4127	0.5429	8.8714	405.3577	4.2503	1011.1119
GISS-E2-2.1-G	7.8221	1.5606	2.5062	0.6418	8.7049	146.5052	3.9324	323.8021
GISS-E2-2-H	7.1082	1.3441	2.6443	0.6175	9.3065	80.1738	4.6890	191.7159
HadGEM3-GC31-LL	6.9687	0.6282	5.5464	0.5363	7.5443	73.4850	6.3372	259.6786
HadGEM3-GC31-MM	7.1628	0.6611	5.4171	0.6180	7.6295	69.7876	5.8123	224.2150
IITM-ESM	9.1013	1.9285	2.3596	0.7470	9.2241	153.6572	3.4313	286.7209
INM-CM4-8	5.6969	1.5557	1.8310	0.7630	6.6724	30.0204	2.8067	60.1268
INM-CM5-0	5.6647	1.4764	1.9185	0.6614	7.9929	48.5134	3.6788	107.9477
IPSL-CM5A2-INCA	6.1823	0.8159	3.7887	0.5504	7.8027	111.1669	5.6454	342.1371

268

269 **Figure F1.** (Currently shows G13 models. Will be replaced with CMIP6 sample as described above)

270 (a) CO₂ concentration derived from Eqns. (3), (5) and (7-9) for the standard TIPMIP-ESM scenario with

271 0.2K per decade warming, followed by stabilisation at a warming of 2.0 K for 100 years, followed by

272 cooling at 0.2 K per decade. (b) the corresponding EBM temperatures for the upper (T , solid) and lower

273 (T_0 , dashed) ocean boxes. A representative sample is shown to illustrate the range of model behaviours.

274 Corresponding plots for all models in Table 1 are in the Supplementary Material. Note there is a slight

275 overshoot of T beyond the target value, resulting from the imposition of continuity of F rather than T_0 in

276 Eqn. (5)

277

278 For AOGCMs not shown in Table 1, and where the full calibration is not readily available, a satisfactory
279 approximate solution can be obtained by using just F_{4x} and λ values (or equivalently, F_{4x} and the Effective
280 Climate Sensitivity *EffCS*) for the specific AOGCM, using multi-model mean values from Table 1 for the other
281 parameters. F_{4x} and λ are easily obtained from the ‘Gregory plot’ (Gregory et al. 2004) derived from the standard
282 *abrupt-4xCO2* experiment, which is widely run during the model development/evaluation process. Figure F2
283 illustrates these approximate solutions, for comparison with the exact solutions shown in Figure F1

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291 **Figure F2.** (Currently shows G13 models. Will be replaced with CMIP6 sample as described)

292 As Figure 1, but using the multi-model mean values for the parameters C , C_0 , and γ . The parameters λ and

293 F_{4x} are taken for each model from Table 1.

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2.6 Testing the method in AOGCMs

Our testing focuses on the temperature stabilisation phase. We have tested the stabilisation protocol using three AOGCMs: CESM1.2 (derived from CESM1.0, Hurrell et al. 2013), HadGEM3-GC31-MM (Williams et al. 2017), and MPI-ESM1-2-HR (Müller et al. 2018). In each case stabilisation at a GWL of 2.0 degC was started from the appropriate point on the existing *lpctCO2* experiment (see Section 2.2), with the CO₂ concentration timeseries calculated using eqns. (5) and (10). Figure F3 shows that the calculated CO₂ concentration gives approximately constant GWL over the 100 years of each run.

As a further confirmation that the method is working as expected, and a comparison with the emissions-driven protocol, we have calculated CO₂(t) using eqn (3), for the case of 0.2 degC per decade rampup, followed by stabilisation at 2 degC GWL, using the parameters for the model UKESM1-1-LL from Table 1. The UKESM1-1-LL model has been run for this case in *emissions-driven* mode, with an active carbon cycle, and produces approximate stabilisation at a GWL of 2 deg C (J26). Therefore an additional check of our method is to compare the CO₂ concentrations that are *calculated* by UKESM1-1-LL with those predicted from equation (3). Figure F4 shows that the emissions-driven protocol closely follows the target temperature timeseries, and that the CO₂ concentrations it produces are very close to those predicted by the EBM. Hence see that Method P provides a good estimate of the CO₂ concentrations needed to follow the desired GWL timeseries.

323

324

325 **Figure F3.** Global SAT in the CESM1, GC3.1-MM and MPI-ESM models under an initial 1pctCO_2 rampup, followed by
 326 stabilisation at GWLof 2.0 degC using method P .

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330 **a**

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335 **Figure F4.** Global mean CO_2 concentrations and temperature for the same scenario as in Figures F1 and
 336 F2, using EBM parameters for the UKESM1-1-LL model (blue), and UKESM1-1-LL parameters but with
 337 multi-model mean values used for C , C_0 and γ (black). The actual values from a run of UKESM1-1-LL
 338 using the standard emissions-driven protocol (Jones et al. 2026) are shown in red; in that run the CO_2
 339 concentrations are predicted by the model and so this provides an independent a posteriori test that the
 340 EBM is producing the correct concentrations.

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3 Method A (Adaptive): Calculation of forcing using adaptive control

In method P, the atmospheric CO₂ concentration is calculated in advance of the ESM simulations. This inevitably involves some approximations, although as we show in Section 2, these provide an acceptable fit to the target SAT timeseries, across a practical range of parameter values. In contrast, method A uses an adaptive algorithm to calculate the required atmospheric CO₂ concentration and update it regularly during the ESM simulation, hence ensuring that the simulated global mean SAT stays close to the target GWL. The algorithm relies on the relationship between the CO₂ forcing and the global temperature, which adapts to the current state of the climate system. This method does not require a calculation of the CO₂ trajectory in advance, and it allows a significant correction of the CO₂ concentration if the simulated temperature deviates too much from the target GWL (for example if additional perturbations such as fresh water hosing are applied to the model to simulate crossing of tipping points, that themselves alter GWL).

3.1 Rampup and rampdown phases

For method A it is proposed that a prescribed CO₂ concentration approach (Method P, Sections 2.1, 2.3) is used for the rampup and rampdown phases. The adaptive approach is applied to the stabilisation phase.

3.2 Stabilisation phase

For the stabilization period, Method A uses the AERA algorithm as a prototype, which was developed for emission-driven ESM simulations (Silvy et al., 2024; Georgievsky et al., 2025). To account for interannual climate variability, the CO₂ emissions in AERA (atmospheric CO₂ concentration in method A) do not respond to annual temperature changes, but to the temperature averaged over a longer period of time. As in the AERA approach, the time period could be 5 years or could deviate depending on the interannual climate variability.

After the start time t_0 of the stabilization period, the change in atmospheric CO₂ concentration is calculated proportionally to the difference between the stabilization GWL, \underline{T} and the actual mean annual global temperature $T(t)$:

$$\frac{dCO_2}{dt} = c_T(\underline{T} - T(t)) \quad (11)$$

378 where c_T , ppm K⁻¹, is a model parameter $\frac{CO_2^{pic}}{TCR}$ that is inversely proportional to the TCR of the ESM.
379

380 **3.3 Testing the method in AOGCMs**

381 We have implemented the method (11) in the CLIMBER2 intermediate-complexity climate model (Ganopolski
382 and Brovkin 2017), using $c_T = 155$ ppm K⁻¹, which corresponds to the TCR of CLIMBER2. The results are shown
383 in Fig. F5 (left), for stabilization at three different GWLs (2, 3 and 4 degC), and following three different rampup
384 pathways. We see that in CLIMBER2 (which has low levels of interannual variability in GMST), the method
385 follows the target GWL very closely. In this case the results are very similar those obtained by adaptive control of
386 the emissions (AERA, Silvy et al. 2024).
387

388 When the method is applied to a CMIP-class AOGCM MPI-ESM-1.2LR, interannual variability of GMST results
389 in a periodic oscillation of the CO₂ concentration (period of around 40 years, visible in Fig. F6, bottom). However,
390 these oscillations are hardly visible in the temperature (Fig. F6, top), which remains near the target value within
391 the range of interannual variability, similar to the AERA algorithm.
392

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Figure F5 Application of Method A (adaptive control) in the intermediate-complexity climate model CLIMBER-2. The method is applied to three different target global warming levels (2, 3, 4 deg C), following three different rampup rates for CO₂ concentration: (a,b) 1% compound p.a., (c,d) 0.5% compound p.a., (e,f) Linear increase following eqn (4), tuned to the TCR of CLIMBER-2. Left-hand panels show GWL, right hand panels show CO₂ concentration. Model years (bottom axis) are arbitrary for these idealized runs.

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408 Figure F6. Application of method A (adaptive control) to the AOGCM MPI-ESM-1.2LR. The model is controlled
 409 to three target warming levels (2, 3, 4 degC), following different rates of rampup. “AER” refers to runs that
 410 participated in the AERA-MIP exercise. FSC refers to runs with an additional contribution from frozen soil
 411 (permafrost) carbon emissions

412

413

414 4. Diagnostics, naming of experiments and files

415 Since for many applications the precise details of the forcing method are unimportant (e.g. impacts studies or
 416 downstream ‘whatif?’ experiments in which tipping processes are induced at a particular GWL by some artificial
 417 forcing (Swingedouw et al. 2026)), we follow as closely as possible the diagnostics and naming conventions used
 418 for emissions-driven runs (Jones et al. 2026), to maximise transparency and discoverability for users of model
 419 data.

420

421 **4.1 Alternative rampup protocols**

422 It is recognised that for practical reasons, some GWL stabilisation runs will be branched from a GWL rampup
423 that is the standard CMIP 1pctCO2 run (Eyring et al. 2016), as this run will frequently be already available. For
424 many models this will result in a somewhat faster (and nonlinear) temperature rampup.

425

426 **4.2 Diagnostics**

427 The diagnostic data request for the experiments described here follows exactly the data request for emission-
428 driven runs, as detailed in Section 3.5 of Jones et al. 2026, with appropriate modifications, for example where
429 models used do not include an active carbon cycle. This should ensure that downstream analysis (e.g. for impacts
430 studies) can access the widest range of possible model output.

431

432 **4.3 File naming conventions and experiment identifiers**

433 *Experiment and file naming conventions are currently under discussion and will be added.*

434

435 **5 Comparison of the different protocols**

436 **5.1 Differences between P and A methods**

437 The main differences between methods P and A are:

- 438 ● Method A only needs TCR, which is probably easy to find in the literature for most GCMs. P requires F_{4x}
439 and Climate Feedback Parameter CFP (or ECS and CFP), maybe less easy to find for some models. But it
440 will be known to GCM modelling groups, and parameter values for CMIP6 models are provided here in
441 Table 1
- 442 ● Method A requires a little coding infrastructure to implement the workflow, while method P does not
443 require modifying the GCM.
- 444 ● Method A is likely to hold closely to the target GMST by construction (but not perfectly due to internal
445 variability). P involves some approximation (e.g. 2-layer model, and the relationship between CO2 and
446 the forcing).
- 447 ● Method A can induce oscillations in the forcing due to the delay in the response of temperature to forcing
448 (and vice versa).
- 449 ● If a tipping (e.g. AMOC) occurs during the run that has an impact on GMST, A will try to restore the
450 GMST (although some issues may arise if the tipping changes the TCR), while P will simply allow the

451 tipping to influence the GMST (also the case for the emissions-driven protocol J26 vs AERA). Possibly
452 cite figure from Laura’s paper to illustrate this effect?

453

454 **5.2 differences between c-driven and e-driven methods**

455 (e-driven = J26 and AERA)

- 456 ● All methods are conditioned on GWL, so they remove effects of model differences that are purely due to
457 differences in global radiative feedbacks/climate sensitivity.
- 458 ● E-driven protocols include effects of C-cycle feedbacks in the response, which may vary in strength
459 between models, and over time. That is useful for some contexts – gives more direct link to possible
460 overshoot mitigation pathways. In other cases c-driven forcing may allow simpler analysis of dynamics
461 of hysteresis responses, and allows exploration using higher resolution models because costly carbon
462 cycle calculations are not needed.
- 463 ● There is likely to be little difference between methods for rampup/stab at ‘lower’ (2C) warming levels
- 464 ● More difference is expected for stabilisation at higher warming levels (>2C), and for rampdown, as
465 carbon cycle feedbacks come more into play in these cases (e.g. ZEC changes at higher GWL)

466

467 **6 Discussion and Conclusions**

468

469 Policy-relevant information is often presented in terms of GWL. Also scientifically, we often want to assess the
470 committed impacts of a certain GWL (e.g. ice sheets driven by ESM output). Hence framing climate model
471 experiments in terms of particular GWL (instead of emissions or concentrations as has commonly been the case)
472 allows a different perspective that in some cases can be more easily related, e.g. to the Paris temperature targets.
473 Adopting a fairly open approach to define ways to bring models to the target SAT evolution (e.g. by allowing
474 methods that specify either emissions or concentrations) allows as many models as possible to participate in
475 standardised comparisons such as TIPMIP, and produces useful diversity in experiments to allow a wider range
476 of questions to be addressed. Note however that *all* these protocols are idealised and intended to develop
477 indicative information on the response to overshoots, and scientific insight into the processes of irreversible
478 change/hysteresis. They are not intended as tools for detailed emissions policy making.

479

480

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485

486 **Data availability**

487 The concentration-driven simulations at the 2°C warming level with HadGEM3, MPI-ESM-HR and CESM1 are
488 available on zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/18303958>

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